

ISic0316

Fragment of an inscription for a civic magistrate

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Serena Agodi,system,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2017.03.21

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory no inventory number

Physical Description

Fragment of cream coloured marble with blue veining.
Broken top, right and below, intact on left. Moulding preserved on left side. The rear is finished and smooth, as is the left edge. The moulding is 3.8 cm wide, set 5cm in from the left edge.

Dimensions

Height 27.1 cm
Width 17.3 cm
Depth 3.8-4.0 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-2: 42-45 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 61 mm

Text

1. [L (ucius) Caelius L (uci) f (ilius)]
2. C | [a] (udia) [Macer]
3. II · v [ir---]
4. [---]

Apparatus

Text restored on the parallel of ISic0337

Text restored on the parallel of ISic0337

Translation (en)

Lucius Caelius Macer, son of Lucius, of the Claudian tribe, duumvir... .

Translation (it)

Lucio Celio Macro, figlio di Lucio, della tribù Claudia, duumviro... .

Commentary

Although none of the texts of ISic0337, 0315 or 0316 join together, and all show minor differences in form or material (e.g. compare the moulding on each), the text presented on each appears to be the same. A manuscript in the Vatican library records a fourth, similar fragment seen in the Museo dei Benedettini by C. Stevenson in the 1880s. The text, which may be common to all these fragmentary inscriptions, can be restored as it has been here.

The texts are probably honorific inscriptions. Marble slabs of this sort are commonly attached to a statue base or similar monument. The base itself would be made out of a different, cheaper, local stone (e.g. volcanic stone), the more expensive imported marble reserved for the inscription. The existence of multiple texts, apparently for the same person, has two possible explanations: either the same honorific inscription was repeated on all four(?) sides of the statue base or other monument; or else there were multiple honorific statues or monuments in Catania for this one individual (both possibilities are attested elsewhere). The remainder of the inscription will have included details of the rest of his career (compare the inscriptions for Quintus Atilius Severus (also of the Claudian tribe) and Lucius Rubrius Proculus). Lucius Caelius Macer is one of five duumviri known from Roman Catania.

Digital identifiers:

TM 491523

EDR 139970

EDCS 21900351

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0316>

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.4022610

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7032 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione*. Helsinki. At 19

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0316. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4335115>